

New etymologies for Daco-Getic (from Ancient Greek attestations) Δάκοι, Δάκαι, Δάος, Δάοι; Phrygian δάος (from Hesychius' Ancient Greek text); Daco-Getic (from Latin attestations) Davus, Dacus, Daca, Daci; Latin Faunus, Illyrian Daunus, Illyrian Δευάδαι/Deuadai (= "satyrs"), Ancient Greek θαῦνον (thaunon); PIE **d^hew-*/**d^heh₂w-*, PIE **d^hews-*, PIE **d^hewh₂*, PIE **mer*, and more

Alexandru Gheorghiu
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Part 1

A number of decades ago, in the mid 20th century, the Dacian-referent terms Δάοι (plural) and Δάος (singular) found in Ancient Greek writings and the Dacian-referent term Davus found in Latin/Roman writings were posited¹ to be cognate to Phrygian δάος meaning "wolf" (an entry in Hesychius of Alexandria's very reliable glossary of obscure Ancient Greek words notes that δάος was a Phrygian word that meant "wolf": the actual Phrygian form was probably *dáwos*²), and it was also posited at that time that the Thracian-derived³ terms Δάκοι, Δάκαι, Dacus, Daca, Daci are also cognate to Phrygian δάος.

After studying the evidence quite well and after studying the competing theories quite thoroughly, I have come to the conclusion that Phrygian δάος is either 1) a cognate from the same root-word, or 2) a semi-cognate ("semi-cognate" is perhaps a new term coined by me) from a kindred root-word.

Phrygian δάος may or may not derive from the PIE root **d^heu*/**d^hew-*/**d^heh₂w-* that meant "to strangle, choke; drown; die; pass away": it is at present too close to call/to be sure either way.

Phrygian δάος may instead derive from a root of different meanings that had a sonic/verbal form identical or nearly identical to **d^heu*/**d^hew-*/**d^heh₂w-*, but the semantic was totally different (even though the two homonym/nearly homonym roots would most likely be kindred roots as I will detail later in this paragraph), and this root (which is found at least in Orel, 1998 as I will detail later) had the root-meaning "force, strength", deriving from a PIE **d^h*="force, strength", found in many (in possibly all, but I haven't checked them all yet) PIE roots beginning with **d^h*: this PIE **d^h*="force, strength" would most likely be the source of both homonym/nearly homonym roots, in which case I would consider them kindred roots.

Such a root is indicated not only by Orel's etymology of Albanian Dak ("big ram"; here "ram" refers to a male sheep) from a PIE **d^hew*/**d^heu* (which he describes as being a variant of PIE **d^hwes-*/**d^hews-* "to breathe (in or out); breath; spirit, soul > creature") via Proto-Albanian **dauka*⁴, but also by the Hesychius gloss Δευάδαι="satyrs among the Illyrians", which I derive from a root

1 I don't yet know who was the first to posit this; it may have been Dimitar Dechev in 1957.

2 According to V. Orel, this word *dáwos*="wolf" also occurs in a Phrygian inscription.

3 These Ancient Greek terms derive from the Daco-Getic variety/varieties of the Thracian branch of Indo-European. Cognates (and possible cognates) in Ancient Greek and Phrygian and other languages will be discussed in this paper.

4 This etymology of the Albanian word Dak was posited by Orel (1998) on the basis of the Albanian word Dash (meaning "ram", not "big ram" like Dak): Dash had been derived (don't yet know by whom) from Proto-Albanian **dauša*, in turn from PIE **d^hows-o-s*, from PIE **d^hews-*; another etymology of Albanian Dash derives it from PIE **d^heh₁(y)-* "to suckle, nurse", but like Orel and others, I don't accept that PIE **d^heh₁(y)-* "to suckle, nurse" etymology for Albanian *Dash*. For the etymology of "dak", see Orel, Vladimir (1998), "dak" in Albanian Etymological Dictionary, Leiden, Boston, Cologne: Brill, p. 54.

meaning “force, strength” leading to “wild, strong, virile, powerful”⁵; and Latin *Faunus* (=Horned god of the forest, plains and fields; Greek counterpart: Pan) also very convincingly argues for a PIE *d^hew which had the same semantic range as PIE *d^hews-: it is unlikely that Latin *Faunus* derives from that root meaning “to strangle” as someone posited in the past (if *Faunus* was associated with the throttling of wolves and lynxes, as a guardian of the sheep-herd, that would change matters; that is something I will try to find out for the next edition). I derive Latin *Faunus* from earlier *d^hhaunus/*d^hhaunos, from a root *d^hew-, meaning “wild, strong, virile, powerful” (the change of initial PIE *D^h- to Latin F- is the standard sound-shift for that sound in that position from PIE to Latin, and I recall no exceptions in Latin); and Illyrian *Daunus* (corresponding in form to *Faunus*), an anthroponym of unknown meaning, more likely meant “strong, virile, powerful” rather than “smotherer, choker, strangler, killer”.

Ancient Greek *θαῦνον* / *thaunon* (“beast”) also likely derives primarily from “wild, strong, virile, powerful” not primarily from “to strangle, choke, smother, kill”: but polysemy is likely, maybe even from the beginning, due to the root being *d^h=“force, strength”.

Other kindred roots would be: PIE *d^hew-, “to run>to flow”; *d^henh₂-, “to set in motion; to flow”; *d^her-, “to support, to hold fast, to hold”, PIE *d^herǵh- “strong; robust; to bind fast; be firm; support”, PIE *d^hers-, “to be bold, to dare”; PIE *d^hreg^h-, “to drag; to pull; to run”; PIE *d^héǵhōm-, “earth” (which I derive from “firm, dense, thick, strong, supporting, covering”, with the “covering” possibility deriving from “thick, dense>obscuring”), PIE *d^heh₁- “to put, place; to do” (for the explanation of this one, see my paper on the origin of PIE *d^heh₁ and on the origin of many other roots beginning with *d^h-), *d^hwes-/ *d^hews- “to breathe (in or out); breath; spirit, soul > creature” (the explanation for this one is in the next paragraph), *d^hewh₂- “smoke, mist, haze” (the explanation is in the next paragraph), PIE *d^hewǵh- “to be strong, have force; to produce; to produce something useful”, PIE *d^heyǵh- , “to form, to shape; to knead”; PIE *d^hāǵ-u-, “to whet, to sharpen” (the explanation is in that other paper, for now see “to produce something useful; to be strong, have force”); and many more.

The PIE root *d^hwes-/ *d^hews- “to breathe (in or out); breath; spirit, soul > creature” I theorize has as its base this *d^h=“force, strength”, leading either to 1) “wind” or 2) to “life-force”, “breath as that which keeps one alive/in strength”: the similarity of PIE *d^hwes- to PIE *h₂weh₁- “to blow (of the wind)” suggests option 1, while the similarity to PIE *d^hwer-, “door, opening, entrance” may indicate that *d^hwer- is from “force>force applied>to push in, push forwards; go in” as the wind pushes forwards; otherwise, again using my theory that PIE word-initial *d^h=“force” (almost always if not always) *d^hwer- may be from “force>force applied>to pierce, bore a hole through”. I prefer the “force>force applied>to push in, push forwards; go in” option.

PIE *d^hewh₂- “smoke, mist, haze” I posit had the root-meaning “thick, dense” or “blowing wind”, both options deriving from *d^h=“force, strength”, leading to “strong, thick, dense, firm” and/or to “wind/blowing air/breath”: the *d^hewh₂- form doesn’t seem to give a good clue as to whether it actually derives from “force>to blow/push/move violently>wind, forceful breath/panting” or from “force/strength>thick, dense”: I suspect that in their minds (the minds of the Pre-PIE word-creators) the two different options were blended and the form could have been used for both: see PIE *d^hew-, “to run>to flow” and PIE *d^henh₂-, “to set in motion, to flow”. PIE *d^heng^h-, “to overcast, to cover; cloud(s)” for sure derives from “force>thick, dense”.

PIE *d^heu/*d^hew-/ *d^heh₂w- “to strangle, choke; drown; die; pass away”: this was a more difficult semantic set/development to explain, though early on before publishing the first draft I saw what I now believe is the correct answer, but I had pushed it aside in favor of another theory: but after trying out

⁵ In the first edition, I posited the semantic progression: “breathe (in or out); breath; spirit, soul > vigorous, powerful, mighty, virile, wild, fierce”. But since then, I determined that the meaning “breath” most likely came from “force”, so it’s no longer necessary to posit the meaning “breath” as one of the steps; it may have been a key step though, which is why I mention this earlier derivation here.

that other explanation⁶ and not finding it good enough, my new theory is that these meanings come from “to cover; to smother; to press upon, to crush”, in turn from “tight, thick, dense, firm”, in turn from “force”: or directly from “force” leading to “to crush, press upon, smother”.

Another word that indicates well that **d^h*=“force, strength” is Ancient Greek θύω=“I rush in, storm, rage, seethe (in general of violent movements)”: compare θύω=“I rush in” to my suggestion that PIE **d^hwer-* “door, opening, entrance” derives from “to enter in, push in”, from **d^h*=“force, strength”. Other meanings of θύω in Ancient Greek are: “slay, kill, burn, immolate; slaughter; consult (of oracles, prophets, hence likely deriving from “sacrifice”); celebrate (likely deriving from “to sacrifice” as well). The meanings of Ancient Greek θύω indicate that I am correct in deriving PIE **d^heu/*d^hew-/*d^heh₂w-* “to strangle, choke; drown; die; pass away” from “force, strength” (cf. “I rage, storm, seethe, in general of violent movements; slay, kill, etc.”). See also Sanskrit *dhūyate*, “to shake, to tremble” (suggesting “wind” as well) and Proto-Slavic **duti*, “to blow, to swell, to blast”. Proto-Slavic **duxàti* “to blow, to puff”. Proto-Slavic **dvoxati*, “to breathe heavily”.

Since it is so likely that the root-meaning of any root from which Phrygian δάος (“wolf”) can derive must have been “force, strength”, it’s no longer necessary to assume (as some probably do, or maybe no one goes so far/went so as to assume that, in the actual sense of the word “assume”) that Phrygian δάος (“wolf”) derives from the meaning “strangler, choker, smotherer” (meanings which in turn, as I described above, most likely ultimately come from “force, strength, strong”): instead Phrygian δάος (“wolf”) may derive from “force” via another path, as did Albanian Dak=“big ram” (here “ram” refers to a male sheep): the path could have been like this: 1) “force, strength”>“wind/breath”>“living creature”>“powerful creature/fierce creature”>“wolf”; or like this 2) “force, strength”>powerful creature/fierce creature>“wolf”. Also very possible though is the derivation of “wolf” from “strangler, choker, smotherer, killer”. And also possible was polysemy, polysemy from the beginning: in other words, all 3 options at the same time.

Words and terms that do derive from the “strangle, choke, drown, die, pass away” root include the *daules/daulas* portion of the Lydian theonym/anthroponym/epithet Kandaules/Kandaulas⁷; likely

6 In the first draft of this paper, I had posited that PIE **d^heu/*d^hew-/*d^heh₂w-*, “to die, pass away, strangle, choke” derive from the earlier meanings “to drown<immerse in water/sink into the water<water/to flow”, and I posited that “to drown/sink into the water” led to “to sink, vanish, sink into the earth, into death, into the other world/the underworld; to pass way, die, drown, suffocate, choke, get strangled” and likely included also was the idea “to flow away”. I posited this after studying the words derived from PIE **d^heu/*d^hew-/*d^heh₂w-*, “to die, pass away, strangle, choke” as well as the words derived from PIE **mer-* “to die; to disappear”, and the words derived from PIE **mesg-*, “to dip, sink”. PIE **mer-* “to die; to disappear” has a homonym PIE root **mer-*, “sea, lake, wetland”, just as PIE **d^hew-* “to die, pass away, strangle, choke” has a homonym PIE root **d^hew-*, “to run>to flow”. The explanation may be that PIE **mer-* “to die; to disappear” derives from “covered, smothered, crushed” from M=“force, strength, strong”, seen also in PIE **melh₂-*, “to crush, grind, break, pound” and in PIE **mew*, “to move” and in various IE and Non-IE words beginning with M- which denote loud sounds. PIE **mesg-*, “to dip, sink, plunge” likely derives from **mes/*meu*=“water” in turn likely from **mes*=“to run, move”, from “force”: compare PIE **mew-*, “to move” (unless, not impossible, the meaning “water, wet” came first, and “to move” developed from the movement of water: but I think the water/wet meanings came later). Proto-Slavic **mosky* meaning “swamp, dampness, moisture” is from **mesg-*, as is known already. From PIE **mesg-* also derives (by rhoticism) Latin *mergō* (from earlier *mezgō*): Latin *mergō* included the meanings: “I dip (in), immerse, plunge into water; drown; I overwhelm; I cover, bury; I sink down or in, plunge; (of water) I engulf, flood, swallow up, overwhelm; (figuratively) I hide, conceal, suppress”. Furthermore, the Romanian descendant of Latin *mergō* is used to mean “go, leave”, as in the phrase “hai să mergem”=“Let’s go”. Compare also the similar PIE **dew-*, “to plunge, sink; to decline”, source of Ancient Greek δύω (=“to cause to sink, to plunge”). I have not yet determined the origin of PIE **dew*, “to plunge, sink, decline”. Despite PIE **mesg*, I don’t think that the **d^heu/*d^hew-/*d^heh₂w-* “strangle, choke, crush, drown, die, pass away” meanings come from “water, wet; to flow”, though that is what I posited in the first draft.

7 Kandaulas/Kandaules was a Lydian epithet used as a theonym as well as the name/epithet of a Lydian king from legendary times: Hipponax called that Lydian king *kunankhes* (=“Dog-strangler”/“Dog-throttler”), and from there and

also the -dāvia/-δαουία portion of the Illyrian/Illyrianesque oronym (mountain-name) Candāvia (Ancient Greek Κανδαουία); perhaps Ancient Greek Thaulios in the Thessalian formula Zeus Thaulios, though no one can say yet whether Zeus Thaulios actually meant “Zeus the Strangler” as has been theorized by someone; Proto-Slavic *daviti, meaning “to drown, choke, suffocate, strangle”; Avestan dauu (“to crush, to oppress”; Avestan *dauu* is attested in the form *duuaidī*, 1 du. past middle); Albanian dekë, vdekë, vdekje meaning “death”; Proto-Germanic *daupuz (“=death”) and *daudaz (“=dead”); and a number of other words, which are described in various reference works.

Whoever first posited that Phrygian δάος derives from the root meaning “to strangle, choke, drown, die, pass away” probably theorized that δάος came from the earlier meaning “strangler”, which would have referred to how a fanged predator usually brings down its prey by sinking its fangs into the neck of the prey, and thereby in a way strangling and often choking the prey (often also breaking the neck) while at the same time wounding seriously with its fangs. That wasn’t a bad idea, but though seemingly quite plausible, that theory is not the only possibility/option.

In the Celtic and Armenian branches of IE, the PIE root *wĺkʷos (“wolf”, from a root-meaning which no doubt was a frightening one, just as “strangler/smotherer/choker/killer” would be) was dropped out of fear, and instead Armenian and Celtic use words for the wolf which most likely⁸ derive from PIE *waylos, a root which likely meant “howler”: and if it meant “howler”, that’s a much more milder meaning than “strangler/smotherer/choker/killer”. So if *wĺkʷos was dropped out of fear in Dacian/Thracian and Phrygian as we see that it was dropped out of fear in Celtic and Armenian, why would they then call the wolf the “strangler, smotherer, choker, killer”? For many people in those times, calling a wolf “strangler, choker, smotherer, killer” would be non-propitious, risky, dangerous, bad juju, and so on.

Even if Phrygian δάος did mean “strangler, smotherer, choker, crusher, killer”, that wouldn’t mean that Δάοι (plural), Δάος (masc. Singular), Δάκοι (plural), Δάκαι (plural) must mean “stranglers”, “smotherers”, “chokers”, “killers”, “crushers”.

Part 2

I posit that Dacian Δάοι (plural), Δάος (masc. singular), Davus (singular), and Δάκοι (plural), Δάκαι (plural), Dacus (masc. singular), Daca (fem. singular), Daci (plural) and Dacisci (plural) derive from a root that had a form like *d^{he}u/*d^{he}w-/*d^{he}h₂w-; and the ultimate derivation was from *d^h=“force, strength”, and the Dacian terms enumerated above developed either from “force>wind/breath>to breathe (in or out); breath; spirit, soul > powerful, fierce” or from “force>powerful, fierce”: for both options I cite and compare Orel’s etymology of Albanian Dak=“big ram”, Δευάδαι=“satyrs among the Illyrians”, Proto-Celtic *dūnom, “stronghold, rampart”, Dacian Dava (which most likely meant “fortress, fortified settlement” rather than just “settlement”: in any case, I derive PIE *d^{he}h₁- “to put, place; to do” from “force”, for reasons explained in another paper), Proto-Slavic *duti = “to swell”.

other key data (such as the Avestan word *dauu* meaning “to crush, oppress” and Proto-Slavic *daviti*=“to strangle, suffocate, choke, drown”) a linguist or other kind of scholar in the 20th century deduced that Kandaules/Kandaulas represents Lydian kan=“dog” from PIE *k^wō (“=dog”) and Lydian daules/daulas=“strangler, throttler” from PIE *d^{he}u/*d^{he}w-/*d^{he}h₂w- (“=to strangle, choke, die, pass away”). I don’t know yet who first published the etymology of Lydian Kandaules/Kandaulas. It may have been in the 19th century, but I doubt it. If in the 19th century, back then the root would have been reconstructed as *dhau or *dheu, something like that. The reconstruction *d^{he}h₂w- is from Rick Derksen and dates from well after the time when the etymology of Lydian Kandaules/Kandaulas was determined and published. The reconstruction *dheu- is found in Pokorny’s IEW from the mid 20th century, though I’m pretty sure the *dheu reconstruction predates Pokorny’s publication.

8 A derivation from PIE *wĺkʷos for Armenian *qayl* (*gayl*) = “wolf” per Martirosyan is unlikely due to great phonetic problems. Martirosyan, Hrach (2010) *Etymological Dictionary of the Armenian Inherited Lexicon* (Leiden Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Series; 8), Leiden, Boston: Brill, page 196.

For the meanings “wild, fierce, powerful” see also the parallel synonymous example of Proto-Germanic *deuzaz meaning “wild, fierce, bold”: Proto-Germanic *deuzaz derives from PIE *d^hews “to breathe (in or out); breath; spirit, soul > creature/powerful creature/fierce/wild creature”.

I posit that the Illyrian and Messapic names with Daz- and Das- are from “strong” as well.

The Dao-/Dawo-/Davo- forms vis-a-vis the Dak- forms can, as seen from the examples of Albanian Dak, Dash and dekë (dekë is from a *d^hew- root, while Dak is from a different *d^hew- root, and Dash is from a *d^hews- root which is a variant of *d^hew), be variants from the same root among kindred languages, even among different dialects of what can be considered one language---and that is all we need; one need not posit that the Dak- forms and the Dao-/Dawo-/Davo- forms are cognates within the same dialect: we have no evidence of that anyway; Dio Cassius stated that the Dacians called themselves Daci, and that is why the Romans called them so. Dio Cassius did not say that they also call themselves Daoi.

I’m quite sure that the primary meanings of the terms Δάοι (plural), Δάος (masc. singular), Davus (singular), and Δάκοι (plural), Δάκαι (plural), Dacus (masc. singular), Daca (fem. Singular), Daci (plural) and Dacisci (plural) were “fierce, mighty, vigorous, powerful” in the Dacian language: not “wolf”. Likely δάος /dakos in Dacian was also used to mean “wolf”, but if so I believe that the older meaning was still known, so it would be like if in English the word for “wolf” also meant “fierce, mighty, vigorous, powerful”: that is not the case in English, but I suspect that was the case in Dacian---with the amendment that they very likely had at least one additional word⁹ for “wolf” not deriving from *d^hew, a word for “wolf” originating from a different root (perhaps a wolf word from PIE *w^lk^wos, “wolf”), a word for “wolf” which specifically and only meant “wolf”, while the daos/*dawos/*davos and *dakos word had a wider set of meanings, most likely including “wolf” and “bear” and “panther” and even “big ram”, from the earlier meanings “fierce, wild, vigorous, powerful”: compare Albanian Dak=“big ram”. At the same time due to the inherent polyseny of the *d^h roots since before PIE times, and as seen with Ancient Greek θύω, the meanings “strangle,, choke, smother, kill” could also have been present in a Dacian δάος /dakos word that meant “wolf, panther” as well as in the ethonyms of the Dacians.

I’m also sure---due to the alternate ethnonyms Daos, Daoi, Davus---that Ancient Greek δάκος , a word translated by the 1940 LSJ as “animal of which the bite is dangerous, noxious beast”, is not¹⁰ cognate to Daci, since, judging from the Ancient Greek lexicon and from various IE cognates/likely cognates, Ancient Greek δάκος clearly comes from an earlier meaning “biter/fanged”; in Ancient Greek we find a number of words cognate to δάκος, including δάκνω=“to bite/bite”; δακνώδης=“biting, pungent, painful”; δακνιστήρ=“biting, stinging”, and a number of others which I need not detail now. These words are thought to derive from PIE *denk-, “to bite”; in any case, I’m sure that the Dak- in the Daci terms does not derive from PIE *denk-, “to bite”, nor from any root of similar meaning. The resemblance is a coincidence, just as the resemblance of Ancient Greek δάκος (“animal of which the bite is dangerous, noxious beast”) to Albanian Dak (=“big ram”).

Hesychius glossed that δακόσσα=πορθῆσαι, which is a form of πορθέω=“destroy, ravage, plunder”; likely δακόσσα derives from δάκος =“animal of which the bite is dangerous, noxious beast”.

9 For example there were at least two words for “wolf” in Latin: *lupus* and *hirpus* (with a variant form *irpus*); *hirpus/irpus* is thought to be a loan from the neighboring Sabines, and is of undetermined etymology as of yet.

10 Nor do I know of a linguist who says they are cognate.

The PIE root *ǵʰwer- “wild; wild animal” might come from “powerful” or from “fanged” in turn from “pointed”, later shifting to non-fanged creatures, or from “striker (animal that attacks people)” as well as “animal to be struck by spear, arrow, etc.”, both in turn from “pointed”---but it’s very likely, perhaps more likely, that PIE *ǵʰwer- derives from “powerful” or from “breath; soul; spirit” leading to “animal; wild animal” and also along a another branch to “vigorous”, “mighty”, “powerful” (deriving from “soulful”/“full of spirit, breath, mana/prana”)---the two branches blending (because many animals are mighty, vigorous and powerful); and from “wild”, “wild animal” came the meaning “fierce”. If so, then the Mycenaean anthroponym qe-ri-jo (=K^{wh}ēriōn) (which derives from PIE *ǵʰwer-) had the same meaning that I posit for Daoi and Daci: “fierce, vigorous”, and K^{wh}ēriōn may have also included “mighty, powerful” as I argue were meanings included in Daoi/Daci.

Part 3

There are a number of reasons why it was thought likely that the Dacian-referent terms Δάος, Δάοι, Δάκοι, Δάκαι, Davus, Dacus, Dacia, Daci, Dage¹¹ and Dacisci are cognate to Phrygian δάος--- and I’m sure that they are cognate, for the reasons discussed in this work. Part 2 will enumerate the main reasons why it was thought likely at the time (to which the reader can now add my reasons described in Part 1 of this work).

- 1) the similarity of the Dacian-referent forms Δάος, Δάοι, Davus and Phrygian δάος meaning “wolf”;
- 2) the fact that Phrygian is an Indo-European language and Phrygian is thought to have originated in the Balkans adjacent to Proto-Greek and Proto-Thracian, which were both also Palaeo-Balkan Indo-European languages;
- 3) the fact that Daco-Thracian and Phrygian are expected to have had many close cognates between them and are expected to have not been extremely different from each other (but this depends on one’s definition of “extremely different”);
- 4) the Dacians used a wolf-headed dragon mascot, especially in battle (the archaeologist Vulpe¹² reduces the impact of this argument somewhat by stating that a wolf-headed dragon mascot was not unique to the Dacians).
- 5) In later Roman times, auxiliaries recruited from the Dacian area were also known as *Phrygi*: it is not known why they were called thus: it could be because of a number of similarities between Dacians and Phrygians: though in actuality, I don’t think that the Dacian nor Thracian languages were that close to Phrygian, they could have been close enough to make many/some Romans think that the languages were very close; plus both groups prominently wore pointed caps; and likely, it could be that the word Daos could mean “wolf” in both Dacian and Phrygian, and if so, this was known to many/some of the Romans, and this, combined with the pointed caps and some other similarities, explains why in later times, auxiliaries from the Dacian area were called Phrygi.
- 6) Other ancient peoples had ethnonyms which may derive from the meaning “wolf”, or were cognate to wolf words: whether any ancient ethnonyms have been confirmed as having meant “wolf/wolves” is a question that may be answered in the next edition. But the ethnonym Lycian/Lycians/Lycia probably not derive from Ancient Greek λύκος (“wolf”) nor is it cognate λύκος (“wolf”): the Lycian word for “wolf”, like in all the Anatolian languages, would have had quite a different form. And the terms Lycia/Lycian are quite certainly connected with the term Lukka found in ancient Anatolian sources, and Anatolian Lukka is likely from PIE *lowk-ó-s “open space, clearing” (referring probably to the open tableland plain of Lycaonia, the land of the Lukka) from PIE *lewk-, “bright”.

11 The form *Dage* (a plural form) is attested on the *Tabula Peutingeriana*, a map from the 13th century AD which may be largely based on a Roman original.

12 Vulpe, Alexandru. In his 2001 work on the Dacians.

Those are the main reasons why it was posited that the Dacian-referent terms (Δάοι, Δάκοι, Δάκκai, Davus, Dacus, Daca, Daci, Dagaе and Dacisci) are cognate to Phrygian δάος meaning “wolf”. I also think that Daos, Δάοι, Δάκοι, Δάκκai, Davus, Dacus, Daca, Daci, Dagaе and Dacisci are either cognate to Phrygian δάος meaning “wolf”, or are semi-cognate, with both sets deriving from kindred roots as described earlier.

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Alexandru Gheorghiu